

DAMAGE SENSING IN FIBER COMPOSITES USING NON-UNIFORMLY DISPERSED CARBON NANOTUBES

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Damage sensing in fiber composites with non-uniformly dispersed carbon nanotubes was studied in this paper. A non-uniformly dispersed carbon nanotube fiber composite was obtained using a fiber sizing agent which contains uniformly distributed CNTs. The infusion of the sizing agent into the fiber preform prior to resin infusion gives rise to high agglomeration of CNTs on the fiber surface and results in electrical conductivities of 2~3 orders of magnitude higher than those of specimens prepared by a calendaring approach. Damage initiation and development of this highly conductive composite under static, cyclic and impact loading have been examined. The electrical response of the specimens enables a quantitative measure of the damage state.

Introduction

Adding small amounts of carbon nanotubes to form an electrically conductive network is a promising approach to monitor damage initiation and propagation in polymeric composites with non-conducting fibers. As micro-cracks propagate in the matrix, the conductive pathways are severed in the percolating network, resulting in changes of the electrical resistance [1-3]. This paper reviews our recent work in damage sensing of composites in which carbon nanotubes were dispersed through a fiber sizing agent. The carbon nanotubes are in an agglomerated morphology in the composites, resulting in a significant enhancement in the composite electrical conductivity. Resistance response of these highly conductive composites

enables effective monitoring of damage propagation under cyclic and impact loadings. Work on an innovative approach to enhance electrical conductivity of fiber composites will also be reported.

Experimental

The material systems consist of bisphenol-f epichlorohydrin epoxy resin for tensile tests and SC-15 epoxy resin for impact characterization. A low viscosity fiber sizing agent (SIZICYLTM XC R2G) which contains well dispersed carbon nanotubes was adopted to disperse carbon nanotubes into fiber composites.

Composite laminates for tensile tests were manufactured with ply lay-up of [0/90₂/0], using a vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) technique. Sizing agent was first infused through the glass fiber preform using conventional vacuum-assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) at room temperature. In order to dry the fibers, the sized preform was put in the oven at 150 °C for 4 hours to volatilize the sizing liquid. To fabricate the fiber composites, the sized fiber fabric was layed-up then epoxy resin was infused into the preform using VARTM technique. The epoxy matrix composites were cured at 130°C for 6 hours under vacuum.

Tensile specimens were prepared by adhesively bonding glass fiber reinforced epoxy end tabs, which are electrical insulators, to the edge of the composite laminate, and specimens were cut into strips with a width of 1.27 mm (0.5 inches) using a slot grinder with a diamond

blade. For the electrical resistance measurement the specimen end tabs were cut to expose the composite laminate and electrodes were applied directly to the ends of specimens by applying silver paint over the width of the exposed specimen on the end tab and anchoring the lead wires. Resistive strain gages were mounted on the surface of the specimens for strain measurement.

In order to investigate the failure mechanisms of the nanotube/glass/epoxy composite, mechanical tests were performed using a screw-driven load frame (Instron 5567) at a fixed displacement rate of 1.27 mm/min (0.05 in/min). For cyclic loading, the specimens were loaded and unloaded at the same rate with progressively increasing peak values of cyclic load with step value of 444 N (100 lbs) until failure. An electrical technique based on the 2-wire direct current measurement method was used to monitor the resistance change of the specimen. A Keithley 6430 voltage-current meter was used to measure the resistance of the specimens by sourcing a constant voltage 20 V and measuring the resulting current.

For the impact damage characterization, six layers of the woven fabric were laid up for resin infusion. The as-received sizing agent was diluted with distilled water at the ratio of 1 to 2. The diluted sizing agent was introduced to the preform first using vacuum-assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) technique. In order to dry the solvent of the sizing agent, the fabric was put in oven at 150 °C for few hours. SC-15 epoxy resin was degassed for 20 minutes under vacuum and infused in to the sized preform at room temperature via VARTM technique. After cured for 2 days at room temperature, the composite was cut into a 6 in by 4 in panel using a diamond saw. In order to place electrodes on the surface edges, a thin layer of silver filled epoxy resin was placed on the two surfaces. A lead wire was put on and a copper tape was applied the top. The electrodes were cured at 90 °C for 20 minutes.

The impact tests were performed on an Instron Datup 8250 drop-weight impact testing machine, as shown in Figure 84. A 0.75 in. (1.91cm) diameter hemispherical head was used to simulate the impact loading. The tup velocity was determined using a light barrier (velocity

detector). A total mass of 10151g impactor is dropped on the specimen from 77.80cm height, at a velocity of approximately 3.8 m/s. The energy was approximately 70 J for each impact. The specimen is placed on rigid supports and clamped during the low velocity impact experiments.

Results and discussion

Figure 1 compares the electrical conductivity of the two types of composites. In the three-roll-mill process, the high viscosity of resin has significant influence on the dispersion of carbon nanotubes, resulting in the highest electrical resistivity. The nanotube-containing sizing agent can significantly increase the glass fiber composite electrical conductivity. After infusing sizing agent into the fiber preform once, the conductivity of the composite is 2~3 orders of magnitude lower than that of three-roll milled composite in the longitudinal and through-thickness direction. After infusing the sizing agent twice, the resistivities in the three directions are further reduced and the resistivity reaches a few ohms-centimeter in the longitudinal direction.

Figure 1. Comparison study of electrical conductivity of different composites showing the significant enhancement of the electrical conductivity by sizing agent [4].

Figure 2. Stress and resistance change response of a sizing agent/glass fiber/epoxy composite under quasi-static loading.

Figure 2 shows the stress and resistance response of a sizing agent/glass fiber/epoxy composite under static loading. $\Delta R/L$ is the resistance change per unit length of the specimen. The first linear increase of resistance at low strain is due to the initial elastic deformation of the composite. The subsequent step-increases in resistance are attributed to microcrackings initiated from the randomly distributed flaws in 90° plies of the laminate. The final sharp increase in resistance occurs when the ply delamination is initiated.

Figure 3 shows the stress and resistance-change response of a sizing agent/glass fiber/epoxy composite with $[0/90_2/0]$ configuration during an incremental tensile cyclic test. Resistance change increase simultaneously with applied tensile loading. In each subsequent cycle after damage is initiated, crack re-opening and elastic deformation followed by new crack formation can be identified in the loading part of the resistance-change curve. After the initiation of damage during the first few cycles, permanent resistance change appears due to the accumulated matrix cracks in the transverse plies. The significant permanent resistance increase continues until the failure.

Figure 3. Stress and resistance-change response of a sizing agent/glass fiber/epoxy composite with applied strain [5].

Figure 4 (a) shows resistance-response behavior of a laminated under impact loading. It can be seen from Figure 4 (a) that resistance-change increase with the impact loadings and a permanent resistance occurs after each impact due to the damage propagation. During the impact, there is an over 120% resistance change. The impact damage extent in the composite can be deduced according to this large resistance change comparing the resistance before and after impact, which offers potential as both a laboratory tool for quantitatively measuring the impact damage extent and as in-serve health monitoring of composite structure.

(a)

Figure 4. (a) Resistance-change response during the impact tests; (b) Resistance-change increase during an impact showing that elastic deformation and creation of new impact damage surfaces.

When a solid is subjected any kind of loading, static or impact, it can absorb energy by two basic mechanisms: (1) creation of new surfaces and (2) material deformation. The material deformation occurs first. If the energy supplied is large enough, a crack may initiate and propagate, thus actuate the second energy-absorbing mechanism. Unlike metal materials, fiber composites only can absorb limited amount impact energy through plastic deformation because of their high stiffness. The majority of the impact damage is absorbed through elastic formation and damage formation. As seen from Figure 4 (b) when the composite experiences an impact, there is a large increase in the resistance change due to the elastic deformation and the new formation of damage from the impact.

$$\Delta R = \Delta R_E + \Delta R_D$$

ΔR_E – Resistance increase due to elastic deformation

ΔR_D – Resistance increase due to new damage formation

During the unloading of the impact, because the closing of some cracks and the re-establishing carbon nanotube contacts, the

resistance recovers 10% due to the elastic deformation. However, the resistance increase from the impact damage yields a large permanent resistance increase.

Conclusions

In this research, damage sensing using electrically conductive network formed by carbon nanotubes for fiber composites was investigated. Damage accumulation and mechanisms subjected to static, cyclic, fatigue and impact loadings were examined. Damage accumulation and failure mechanisms of cross-ply laminate under tensile loading were investigated. Careful measurements tracking the accumulation of damage during cyclic loading shows that the damage states transition can be sensed and clearly divided into three stages: crack initiation, transverse microcracking and delamination. Elastic deformation and new damage formation during impacts could also be verified through monitoring resistance change.

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